

A PHENOMENOLOGICAL INQUIRY ON THE EXPERIENCES OF COLLEGIAL MEMBERS: PRODUCTION OF STUDENT PUBLICATIONS IN FOCUS

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A Phenomenological Inquiry on the Experiences of Collegial Members: Production of Student Publications in Focus

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Abstract

The study centered on describing the experiences, coping mechanisms, and personal insights of the members of the Collegial, the official student publication of Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Technology. The aim was to determine the experiences, coping mechanisms, and insights encountered by these members. A qualitative, phenomenological research design was utilized, involving 14 participants from the Collegial. It was found that the members experienced difficulties due to time constraints, the need to equip themselves with research and communication skills, facing criticism in the organization, and dealing with inadequate resources. In terms of coping mechanisms, several themes emerged from the informants' responses: managing time strategically, maintaining open communication and effective collaboration, being motivated by passion and purpose, adhering to truth, and fostering trust. Insights revealed included conducting mock examinations as essential, recognizing teamwork as a catalyst for success, advocating for the unheard and empowering individuals to achieve excellence, and the necessity of possessing versatility and flexibility. The study emphasizes the need for strong support systems, mental health services, and open communication to enhance Collegial members' learning and well-being. It also advocates for further research across diverse educational environments to improve journalism education and student welfare comprehensively.

Keywords: *collegial members, student journalists, articles, phenomenology, qualitative research*

Introduction

One of the most challenging activities that humans have ever engaged in is writing. It necessitates a variety of cognitive processes, including the generation of design ideas, the building up of knowledge representations in the mind, and the accumulation of knowledge from a variety of different experiences. Some of the fields that have investigated the cyclical and nonlinear processes of writing by novice and experienced authors include cognitive psychology, stylistics, rhetoric, text linguistics, critical literary theory, hypertext theory, second language acquisition, and writing pedagogy. There has been journalism on campuses for over ten years. It has unquestionably had an impact on the students' lives. Due to its enormous impact on students' opinions and behavior, campus news has been recognized as crucial (Asperga, 2017).

In a global setting, specifically in Brazil, a study discovered that students who participated in the educational study had difficulties putting their ideas on paper. The students acknowledged their writing challenges, which the Functional Literacy Indicator indicated to be a pervasive problem. According to the Paulo Montenegro Institute, 29% of Brazilians aged 15 to 64 years are functionally illiterate and struggle to read and write in everyday life; for example, they struggle to recognize information on a poster. Students' writing difficulties may also be linked to the findings of the Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA), which show that Brazil's reading level has been consistent over the last 10 years (OECD, 2019; Paulo Montenegro Institute, 2018).

In a national setting, particularly in the schools of the Division of Zambales, the campus journalists generally encountered problems in the different journalistic categories. In terms of news writing, they faced challenges in the proper news headline writing, and careful use of words with controversial elements. In feature writing, the choice of a creative title and the creative presentation of facts in the story were cited as their primary challenges. Lastly, the journalists faced difficulties in copyreading in terms of the use of a complete statement in the headline and checking the facts (Uy, 2020).

With these in mind, this should be taken into consideration when conducting the study. It is essential because it addresses the challenges faced by campus journalists in article writing. As the campus publication serves as the school's official news source, informing readers about school events and activities, understanding these challenges is crucial. This study is significant as it sheds light on the experiences of those involved in producing student publications, highlighting the importance of their role in the school's communication efforts. More importantly, the idea has significant social value because it might act as a theoretical foundation for writers at the institution where this study was conducted to develop their article-writing abilities. Through the results of this study, writing workshops for college campus journalists can be introduced. In light of all of these presumptions, it prompts me to propose this study.

Further, several research has been undertaken about this to fill in the gaps of this study. Related studies such as Joung, (2020) and Mook, (2020) focus mainly on the impact brought by the Covid-19 pandemic which states that campus journalists are having trouble getting interviewees to cooperate for the publication of their campus papers, as well as the journalists refrain from conducting face-to-face interviews to avoid health risk. Also, according to American College Health Association, (2019) and Grubic et al., (2020) it focuses on the difficulty of campus journalists in balancing their academic, mental health, and publication obligations. This research, however, focuses on the experiences of student journalists, including how they construct their articles, how they cope, and how they perceive themselves as student writers at their schools.

Research Questions

This study aimed to explore the experiences of Collegial members of Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Technology in the production of student publications. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the experiences of the Collegial members with regards to the production of student publications?
2. What are the coping strategies of the Collegial members with the challenges in the production of student publications?
3. What are the insights of the Collegial members can share with regards to the production of student publications?

Methodology

Research Design

This study used a qualitative research approach based on phenomenology to better understand the in-depth investigation of the informants' experiences. This method was intended for use by qualitative researchers. It utilized in-depth and focused studies of small groups of people to guide and support the construction of hypotheses. The results of the qualitative research were considered descriptive rather than predictive (Neubauer, et al., 2019). Additionally, the method helped the researcher build connections with the participants. To make the data more trustworthy and genuine, the researcher reported to the participants for additional explanation and verification.

In this study, a phenomenological approach aligned with qualitative research design was used, as it was the most appropriate methodology for investigating the experiences of collegial members involved in the production of student publications. Furthermore, this study did not employ correlational or experimental methods to examine different interventions or quantify variables.

The research design employed in this study is qualitative, specifically utilizing phenomenology as the methodological approach. Phenomenology focuses on capturing firsthand accounts of a particular phenomenon, aiming to challenge existing assumptions about human experiences, emotions, and responses to specific situations. It enables researchers to explore the perceptions, viewpoints, understandings, and emotions of individuals who have directly encountered or lived through the event or circumstance under investigation (Hirsch, 2015). In essence, phenomenology involves a direct exploration and description of phenomena as experienced consciously by those involved in those experiences (Biemel & Spiegelberg, 2017).

In this study, the researcher employed a phenomenological approach to collect and analyze data concerning the experiences of collegial members involved in producing student publications. The focus was not only on understanding the challenges they encountered but also on how they navigated these challenges and what they learned from this distinctive production method. By examining the firsthand perspectives of the collegial members, the study aimed to gain insights into the effectiveness and impact of the production process on their overall experiences.

Participants

In this phenomenological study, participants were drawn from the members of the Collegial a student publication at Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Technology, all of whom had experience in writing articles for student publications. A total of 14 individuals were carefully selected as research participants. Seven of them participated in in-depth interviews (IDIs), while the other seven took part in a focus group discussion (FGD) where they gathered in one location to discuss their responses to the researcher's questions.

Following Creswell's (2013) recommendation for qualitative studies to include between 3 and 15 participants, this study adhered to that guideline. This ensured sufficient information was gathered during the data collection process, which was essential for a thorough analysis.

The researcher employed purposive sampling to select participants, ensuring that only those who could provide relevant information were included. This method involved choosing participants based on specific criteria, rather than relying on chance, which helped ensure that the experiences shared were genuine. By selecting individuals directly involved in the study's topic, this sampling method allowed for a deeper exploration of real-life experiences (Ellis, 2016).

The researcher adhered strictly to the aforementioned requirements during the recruitment procedure. Firstly, each participant had to be a Collegial member studying at Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Technology (KCAST) in Kapalong, Davao del Norte. Secondly, the participant had to be a student enrolled at KCAST. Lastly, the participant needed to have been an associate of the Collegial involved in school publications from 2020 to 2023. On the other hand, participants who were not students of the Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Technology (KCAST) Collegial during the designated 2020–2023 period were excluded from this phenomenological study. To guarantee relevance to the study's focus, those without any prior experience writing for student newspapers were also not qualified.

Procedure

In qualitative research, various methods were used to collect data. The most common techniques included Focus Group Discussions (FGDs) and In-depth Interviews (IDIs). These qualitative data collection methods aimed to provide insights into the processes behind

observed outcomes and to assess changes in people's perspectives (Sutton, 2015).

The researcher followed specific procedures to collect data and relevant information for the study. Initially, consultation with the adviser was crucial to determine the research approach and methodology.

During the study, a voice recorder was employed as a key tool to capture spoken information and expressions directly from the participants. This device was essential for recording clear audio during interviews, providing vital data for analysis.

The voice recorder, although not capturing visual cues like facial expressions, played a significant role in documenting the interviews effectively. Its use ensured reliable and credible data collection throughout the study.

Overall, the voice recorder was instrumental in providing trustworthy information and concrete evidence for the research. It served as a critical tool for gathering and preserving valuable insights from the participants.

It was essential for the researcher to fully grasp the research's nature and objectives to communicate effectively with the participants and obtain their consent to proceed with the study. The strategies employed to collect the necessary data were as follows: initially, the researcher utilized purposive sampling to select the participants. Subsequently, letters requesting permission to conduct the study were sent to the Office of the Vice President for Academic Affairs at Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Technology. These steps were instrumental in ensuring the study could proceed smoothly and ethically.

Participants were encouraged to carefully read and comprehend the consent and agreement forms before signing them. These documents outlined that participation was voluntary and stressed the importance of sharing their expertise, which was critical to the study's outcomes. Additionally, a study orientation session was provided to informants, introducing the purpose, duration, and confidentiality of the interviews. The researcher acknowledged the participants' contributions and ensured they benefited from their involvement. Each informant was treated individually in both focus group discussions and in-depth interviews to gather their perspectives and experiences. Ultimately, participants became research partners, collaborating with the researcher to disseminate the study's findings for academic purposes (Creswell, 2013).

During interviews, the researcher recorded responses from informants and participants using smartphones. Audio recordings were transcribed and translated from the original language into standard English. The emerging themes were then identified through thematic analysis. A data analyst with expertise in language studies reviewed and verified the extracted themes (Creswell, 2013).

Lastly, the results of the interviews were presented, transcribed, and discussed. The information was analyzed, explored, and treated based on the problems of the study. To concretize the idea, the results were supported by related studies and literature.

Data Analysis

The data gathered in this research was presented and analyzed based on the needs and objectives of this research endeavor. This implies that data reduction was performed by selecting, focusing, and simplifying the vast amount of information from participants' responses to ensure the most relevant data was used. Sufficient analysis of the content was conducted to generate the study's findings. Data display was employed to organize and present the reduced data in a meaningful way, allowing for easier interpretation and comparison of patterns. Therefore, data analysis aims at inspecting, cleansing, transforming, and modeling data to discover useful information, propose conclusions, and support decision-making. In addition, the goal of data analysis is to generate knowledge about common patterns and themes in human experience. This process is repeated with each new interview or account until all have been compared.

According to Lune & Berg (2017), data analysis in qualitative research involves systematically exploring and organizing interview transcripts, observation notes, or other non-textual materials. This process enabled the researcher to gather insights and enhance public understanding of the phenomenon or research topic.

In this study, the researcher focused on analyzing the transcripts from both the individual in-depth interviews (IDIs) and the group discussions (FGDs) of selected participants. The data underwent several stages of processing to uncover the study's findings.

Initially, the researcher used coding to categorize minor but frequently interconnected ideas found in the data. This process allowed initial concepts to emerge from the extensive information gathered during the in-depth interviews and focus group discussions.

According to Cohendet and Edward Steinmueller (2000), coding involves identifying passages or data items, searching for concepts, and finding relationships among them. In my study, I employed coding to categorize and label the ideas conveyed in each participant's responses during the IDIs and FGDs. Each response was coded based on the underlying idea it represented.

In this study, the researcher used the coding process to categorize and label the content concepts described in each participant's response during the in-depth interviews (IDIs) and focus group discussions (FGDs). Each response was coded according to the concept it represented.

On the other hand, thematic analysis was employed to identify, analyze, and present patterns within a large dataset. The focus was on generating thick, rich, and detailed descriptions. Thematic analysis was used to explore commonalities among the concepts or codes derived from the coding process. After completing the thematic analysis, key ideas were developed from the coded concepts. These

key ideas extracted from each response formed the core themes. Once the core themes were identified, concepts were clustered together to form cohesive themes that encapsulated the main concepts uncovered in the study's findings (Maguire & Delahunt, 2017).

In this study, thematic analysis was employed to identify patterns among the concepts or codes obtained through the coding process. This involved generating major themes from the data. Following the thematic analysis, core ideas were formulated based on the significant notions found in each response coded. Once the core ideas were established, those related to the same theme were grouped into clusters. This method facilitated the creation of cohesive themes that encapsulated the central concepts emerging from the study's findings.

Ethical Considerations

To guarantee the effectiveness of the conduct of this paper as well as to ensure the safety of the participants involved in this study, this study will strongly align with the highest ethical principles and these are the following: respect for persons, beneficence, justice, consent, and confidentiality. (Mack et al., 2005).

Respect for persons was observed as the researcher refrained from exploiting any vulnerabilities of the research participants. Autonomy was prioritized by maintaining respectful relationships based on trust and confidence between the participants and the researcher. The identified respondents were verbally approached to gauge their willingness to share their experiences and participate in interviews as study participants before the interviews commenced. Additionally, the researcher meticulously planned the interview schedule to minimize the likelihood of participants needing to reschedule or cancel due to other commitments (Creswell, 2013).

In this study, the researcher created informed consent forms for the participants. These forms were sent to the selected participants before the study progressed. Before conducting the interviews, the researcher sought permission from each participant to record their interview sessions. Establishing rapport and building trust and confidence with the participants was a priority. Participants were also allowed to ask the researcher any questions they had before, during, or after the interviews. Importantly, the researcher ensured strict confidentiality of all aspects of the future IDIs and FGDs. Participants were informed of their right to be informed about the study results.

Beneficence required the researcher to focus on minimizing risks for participants rather than maximizing benefits. Participant identities were kept confidential throughout the study to ensure their protection. All data were securely stored and no information was overlooked or left unsecured (Creswell, 2013). Participants' identities were disguised using pseudonyms to prevent the sources of their statements and responses from being identified.

In this study, the researcher took measures to minimize participant risk. Ensuring the well-being of both the interviewer and interviewees was a priority before conducting the in-depth interviews (IDIs) and focus group discussions (FGDs).

Subsequently, to ensure the safety of all participants, a secure venue was selected where face-to-face interviews between participants and researchers could take place. This environment provided participants with a safe space to share their experiences without fear of rejection or judgment. All information files were securely handled to protect participants throughout the study.

Finally, sensitive topics were carefully avoided in the interview guide questions to prevent participants from feeling vulnerable. Both the group discussions and individual interviews were conducted in a manner that prioritized the comfort and well-being of the participants.

Justice required a fair distribution of risks and rewards based on the findings of the investigation. Therefore, it was important to acknowledge the contributions of each participant because they were crucial to the study's success. All participants received proper credit for their efforts in the study.

In this study, the researcher ensured that all participants were treated fairly. Measures were taken to safeguard participant anonymity and confidentiality. The researcher refrained from disclosing personal biases or interpretations while discussing the study's potential conclusions.

Furthermore, participants were given sufficient notice and were kept informed about the interview process as it unfolded. Biases were strictly avoided, and the researcher ensured that participants felt comfortable throughout the interviews. Responses to participants were handled with impartiality whenever they expressed their perspectives on specific subjects, demonstrating objectivity and professionalism. Confidentiality was maintained throughout the study, ensuring the safety of all data and participants. A coding system and pseudonyms were employed to protect participant identities. All resources containing sensitive information, such as videotapes, encoded transcripts, and notes, were destroyed after data analysis (Maree & Pieterse, 2007). Although participants were assured of the confidentiality of their responses, there were instances during the interviews when some participants hesitated to answer questions. The researcher always kept in mind the voluntary and uncoerced nature of participants' disclosure of information.

In this study, the researcher ensured that data obtained through voice recordings, encrypted transcripts, notes, and other materials were protected against exposure and leakage. Personal information collected from participants was encrypted and securely stored to safeguard their privacy. Furthermore, pseudonyms were used to anonymize and protect the identities of the study participants.

Consent was another crucial method for respecting people during the research process. It involved informing all participants about the goals and purpose of the study they were participating in. This ensured that participants were respected throughout the investigation (Creswell, 2013).

In this study, participants were encouraged to make informed decisions and join voluntarily. The researcher ensured that everyone who participated did so willingly. Obtaining consent from participants to record their responses and share their experiences was crucial for gathering data. Participants were also informed about their rights, including the opportunity to ask questions during the interview, the option to end the interview at any time without explanation, and the right to decline to answer sensitive questions. The researcher respected the participants' choice to withdraw from the interview if they chose to do so.

Results and Discussion

Participants

The participants of this study were the Collegial members of Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Technology (KCAST). As illustrated in Table 1, there were (14) people involved in this study: seven (7) for the focus group discussion and seven (7) for the in-depth interview.

In-depth Interview. Seven key informants in this study were the Collegial members of Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Technology. Each person who took part in the in-depth interview was given a pseudonym to protect their anonymity, by the principles of confidentiality, which assignment was made according to their choice and tag names. Assignment of pseudonyms was made according to their unique physical characteristics, their answers, and attitudes shown during the interview sessions. This, Intelligent was the nickname given to the informant because of how it reflects the way she answered the questions provided. Optimistic was the nickname given to the informant because it reflects his personality, while Focus was the nickname given to the participant since it reflects the way he answers the questions. Active was the nickname given to the participant as she actively participated during the interview, while straight-forward was the nickname given to the participant because it reflects how she directly gave her answers. Smart was the given nickname to the participant as it reflects her, while Criticism was the nickname given to the participant since her answers were prone to criticism throughout the interview.

Focus Group. In the same manner, seven participants of the focus group discussion were also given pseudonyms. They were nicknamed as Editor, White, Serious, Loud, Silent, Calm, and Happy. The editor was nicknamed the participant who is good in editing skills, while White was nicknamed because of her skin color. Serious was nicknamed to the participant who was serious throughout the interview, while Loud was the given nickname to the participant as he loudly spoke his answers to the given questions. Silent was nicknamed to the participant who has a small voice, while Calm was the given nickname to the participant who was very calm during the interview, and Happy was nicknamed to the participant who was very smiley during the entire session.

Both groups answered the same set of questions. The participants were selected according to their involvement and experiences of being a Collegial member, in which it was identified by the researcher and verified by the personal declaration of the participants.

Table 1. *Participants of the Study*

<i>In-Depth Interview (Pseudonyms)</i>	<i>Age</i>	<i>Sex</i>	<i>Code</i>
Intelligent	24	Female	IDI-01
Optimistic	24	Male	IDI-02
Focus	23	Male	IDI-03
Active	24	Female	IDI-04
Straight-forward	20	Female	IDI-05
Smart	20	Female	IDI-06
Criticism	21	Female	IDI-07
Total = 7			
<i>Focus Group Discussion (Pseudonyms)</i>	<i>Age</i>	<i>Sex</i>	<i>Code</i>
Editor	21	Male	FGD-01
White	23	Female	FGD-02
Serious	21	Female	FGD-03
Loud	22	Male	FGD-04
Silent	23	Female	FGD-05
Calm	22	Male	FGD-06
Happy	23	Male	FGD-07
Total = 7			
Grand Total = 14			

The in-depth interview and focus group discussion were conducted through the combination of both face-to-face and social media platforms as it will be more convenient to conduct interviews. The researcher did respect the participants' decision if they were asked face-to-face, via messenger audio call, and Google Meet. As to their convenience, five (5) of the in-depth participants chose to be questioned through online social media platforms and two (2) chose to be questioned face-to-face. While the focus group discussion

was conducted through messenger audio call and face-to-face, one (1) of them chose to respond through messenger audio call as it was convenient for the participant and six (6) of them chose to respond face-to-face. The researcher did consider the face-to-face and messenger audio call as an important factor to consider in achieving and ensuring the validity and credibility of the study.

Categorization of Data

After conducting in-depth interviews and focus group discussions, the messenger audio call and face-to-face recording were transcribed, translated, and analyzed. The analysis began with the coding process. To provide meaning to data, the process of coding divides texts into smaller and smaller chunks. A description of the people's environment and groupings of topics for investigation are generated via the coding procedure. The study's overarching description was shaped by these topics. A table with the compiled data was provided. The information acquired was then sent to the data analyst for examination of patterns and trends.

The themes, sometimes called key themes, were provided by study questions to classify the data. The study's overarching topics were dissected at length for the sake of elucidation. The most important points of the respondents are shown in the table next to the overarching themes.

The second step was the data analysis which we settled on as presented in Table 2. The data was organized thematically by presenting the themes in response to each study question. The co-ideas from the participants' replies were the opposites of the major topics in the table. The frequency of the answers was also tabulated, providing the data for the third column in the table that was used to determine which answers belonged to the "generic," "typical," and "variant" categories (Amparo, 2011).

Research Question No. 1: What are the experiences of the Collegial members with regards to the production of student publications?

To answer this research question, an in-depth interview and focus group discussion were conducted with the informants, respectively, hence, several sub-questions were asked.

The major themes and core ideas for research question number 1 are presented in Table 2. From the answers of the participants, four major themes emerged: experiencing difficulty due to time constraints, equipping oneself with research and communication Skills, facing criticism in the organization, and having challenges due to inadequacy of resources.

Table 2. *Experiences of Collegial Members as They Write Articles for School Publication*

<i>Emerging Themes</i>	<i>Supporting Statements</i>
Experiencing Difficulty Due to Time Constraints	<p>"If you are a student-writer, your time management skills will be tested. How will I be able to write those articles immediately while having those responsibilities as a student." — IDI-04</p> <p>"One of the commonly perceived challenges is time constraints since all of us are busy because I do have my own errands as well, relating to my academic journey, and academic pursuits." — IDI-05</p> <p>"First is the time limitations or time constraints, since we are rushing the paper to be published and it will push you to do something. So, I will be meeting deadlines, and as a writer, it is not just one section in your paper that you are dealing with." — IDI-06</p> <p>"Meeting deadlines, since I am not a full-time journalist but also a student. Balancing academic commitments with the demands of writing and editing articles." — IDI-07</p> <p>"One of the challenges that I would emphasize is the time constraint for the reason that, most of the time we write on the spot and we have to post as early as possible on our Facebook page. So, I see it as a challenge because there is a risk that the quality of the articles that I write can be compromised." — FGD-01</p> <p>"I do encounter challenges, especially time constraints. Before I publish the articles, of course, I will check those articles." — FGD-02</p> <p>"For me, time is the problem, since this is not the only thing I do. I have also my responsibilities as a student." — FGD-05</p> <p>"Time conflict, since there are instances that I, myself, or other correspondents are not available in that specific time or event." — FGD-06</p>
Equipping Oneself with Research and Communication Skills	<p>"First skill is, of course, research skills, because I cannot produce something or I cannot prepare a certain publication without applying my research skills." — IDI-05</p> <p>"Having a good writing skill is something that would allow me as a writer to express my idea to the readers." — IDI-06</p> <p>"Interviewing skills, since it is part of my job to do interviews. Especially, we do have this episode called "Chikahan with KCASTians." So, I have to enhance my interviewing skills since I will be interacting with students." — IDI-07</p> <p>"The skills that I mostly used in preparing the articles for publication is critical thinking skills, since in writing articles we need to convey factual information coherently." — FGD-01</p> <p>"Especially in writing, I mostly used critical thinking skills because every time that I will write articles, I also consider the most accurate angle of the story for me to capture the interest of the audience, especially students." — FGD-02</p> <p>"I foster creativity skills in writing, and also because of the school publication, it helped me to develop my</p>

Facing Criticism in the Organization	<p>creativity, especially in writing, and also it allows me to express myself as a writer.” — FGD-06</p> <p>“As a new bloom member or writer, the common challenge that I mostly encounter is you will experience criticism at its finest.” — IDI-06</p> <p>“I am very prone to criticisms, especially in times that we publish our articles, and most especially if I am the one who is tasked to cover a certain event.” — IDI-07</p> <p>“I have been prone to criticism because of having tight deadlines. Criticism is inevitable, most especially if I am that pressured when it comes to writing the articles.” — FGD-04</p>
Having Challenges Due to Inadequacy of Resources	<p>“One common difficulty that I want to address within our organization is criticism. I do encounter criticism that can be a motivation and a criticism that will make you feel down” — FGD-07</p> <p>“The identified constraints that I perceived in preparing and producing student publications include limited resources because I know that not all the time that we have the access to different resources as well as the access to information.” — IDI-05</p> <p>“We have limited materials such as cameras, printers, and laptops that we can use to produce real-time outputs on time.” — IDI-06</p> <p>“Limited resources are one thing that I have observed in our organization. Like having limited printing materials and more.” — IDI-07</p>

Experiencing Difficulty Due to Time Constraints

The members of the Collegial expressed facing difficulties, particularly due to time limitations, while preparing and producing student publications. In-depth interviews and focus group discussions unveiled the challenges associated with managing time constraints during the process of preparing and producing student publications.

Active (pseudonym) mentioned that being a student writer requires effective time management skills to balance academic responsibilities with the demands of writing articles. She must effectively manage her time to balance authoring articles with her academic obligations. She emphasizes how crucial scheduling, prioritization, and effective writing techniques are to success in both fields. She stated:

“If you are a student-writer, dira pud ma test imong time management skills. Unsaon nimo pag sulat sa articles sa daghang trabahuon bilang isang estudyante.” (IDI-04)

(If you are a student-writer, your time management skills will be tested. How will I be able to write those articles immediately while having those responsibilities as a student.)

Furthermore, Straight-forward (pseudonym) mentioned that time constraints are a common challenge due to busy schedules, including personal errands and academic pursuits. Time limits were a typical issue she had to manage her academic pursuits and personal errands. She emphasizes how challenging it is to manage these conflicting obligations within a hectic schedule. She stated:

“One of the commonly perceived challenges include time constraints, since all of us are busy because I do have my own errands as well, relating to my academic journey, and academic pursuits.” (IDI-05)

Moreover, Smart (pseudonym) mentioned the impact of time constraints on publishing papers, emphasizing the necessity of adhering to deadlines. She also acknowledged the multifaceted nature of writing, which involves managing multiple sections of a paper.

Overall, she emphasizes the need for effective time management and multitasking skills in the publishing process. She stated:

“First is the time limitations or time constraints, since especially if we are rushing the paper nga dapat na siya ma publish, so you have to rush on to that. So, I will be meeting deadlines, and as a writer, it is not just one section in your paper that you're dealing with.” (IDI-06)

(First is the time limitations or time constraints, since we are rushing the paper to be published and it will push you to do something. So, I will be meeting deadlines, and as a writer, it is not just one section in your paper that you are dealing with.)

In addition, Criticism (pseudonym) mentioned that it is difficult to balance deadlines between being a part-time journalist and a student, managing academic obligations alongside writing and editing articles. She emphasizes how difficult it is to successfully balance these two responsibilities. She stated:

“Meeting deadlines, since we are all students diba, and dili lang man pd kay kana lang amoa trabaho, we have extra curriculars, kanang naa pud jud tay academics po.” (IDI-07)

(Meeting deadlines, since I am not a full-time journalist but also a student. Balancing academic commitments with the demands of writing and editing articles.)

Additionally, Editor (pseudonym) mentioned the time constraints in writing and posting articles on Facebook, expressing concern that the rush may compromise article quality. He highlights the difficulty of writing under time restrictions for instant publication. He also stated that the pressure to release articles fast could degrade the caliber of the work that is done. He stated:

“One of the challenges that I would emphasize is the time constraint for the reason that, most of the time we write on the spot and we have to post as early as possible on our Facebook page. So, I see it as a challenge because there is a risk that the quality of the articles that I write can be compromised.” (FGD-01)

Further, White (pseudonym) mentioned that she faces challenges, mainly time constraints, and she has difficulties with publishing articles, especially when there are deadlines. She does, however, prioritize checking the articles and putting quality first by carefully reviewing their writings before they are published. She stated:

“I do encounter challenges, most especially sa time constraints kay before mi mag publish og article, of course, gina check mana namo tanan.” (FGD-02)

(I do encounter challenges, most especially time constraints. Before I publish the articles, of course, I will check those articles.)

Consequently, Silent (pseudonym) mentioned that she identifies time constraints as a major issue because they have student responsibilities in addition to their current tasks. She points out that juggling their time between writing tasks and academic obligations is challenging, highlighting the need for efficient time management techniques. She stated:

“Oras jud ang hadlang as in preparing and producing publication, since dili lang man kani atoang gina atubang, so daghan pag mga responsibility as a student dili lang kay as a writer.” (FGD-05)

(For me, time is the problem, since this is not the only thing I do. I have also my responsibilities as a student.)

Further, Calm (pseudonym) mentioned that he identifies time constraints as a major issue because they have student responsibilities in addition to their current tasks. Conflicts of this nature may prevent timely reporting or coverage of significant subjects or occurrences. It alludes to a possible disturbance in the coordination or workflow necessary for good reporting or journalism. He stated:

“Time jud, mag conflict mi sa time and naay kanang dili available ani na oras or ani na event” (FGD-06)

(Time conflict, since there are instances that I, myself, or other correspondents are not available at that specific time or event.)

Equipping Oneself with Research and Communication Skills

The Collegial members suggest that they are acquiring and honing skills related to conducting research effectively and communicating their findings. This skill set is likely essential for their roles as official writers, enabling them to produce high-quality content for the publication.

Straight-forward (Pseudonym) mentioned that it is an essential role for her to have research skills in creating content and preparing publications for the school publication. She emphasizes how important it is to have the capacity to perform thorough research to provide content and establish knowledgeable opinions. She stated:

“First skill is, of course, research skills, because I cannot produce something or I cannot prepare a certain publication without applying my research skills.” (IDI-05)

Additionally, Smart (pseudonym) mentioned that having significant strong writing skills allows her to express her thoughts to the audience and enables her to effectively convey ideas to readers. She contends that engaging an audience and communicating meaning requires the capacity to speak coherently and clearly. She can communicate their thoughts with clarity, impact, and precision when she writes well, which raises the quality of their work as a whole. She stated:

“Having a good writing skill is something that would allow me as a writer to express my idea to the readers.” (IDI-06)

Furthermore, Criticism (pseudonym) mentioned that she needs to enhance her interviewing skills for conducting student interactions in the "Chikahan with KCASTians" episode, which is part of her responsibility. It implies that conducting successful interviews is an essential part of their duties. She hopes that by improving their interviewing abilities, they will be able to hold insightful and interesting interviews with students, which will lead to deep discussions and relationships. She stated:

“Interviewing skills, since part sa among job na mag interview. “Chikahan with KCASTIANS”, we do have this episode na ingon ana so we have to enhance our interviewing skills, since of course mag atubang man jud mig mga estudyante.” (IDI-07)

(Interviewing skills, since it is part of my job to do interviews. Especially, we do have this episode called “Chikahan with KCASTians.” So, I have to enhance my interviewing skills since I will be interacting with students.)

In addition, Editor (pseudonym) mentioned that he utilizes critical thinking skills to convey factual information coherently in articles prepared for publication. It implies that information analysis, differentiating facts from opinions, and presenting information coherently all depend on critical thinking. He makes sure that the articles they write accurately and effectively present factual information by using critical thinking techniques. He stated:

“The skills that I mostly used in preparing the articles for publication is critical thinking skills, since in writing articles we need to convey factual information in a coherent manner.” (FGD-01)

Moreover, White (pseudonym) mentioned that she uses her critical thinking skills, especially in writing articles, to identify the most accurate angles that can capture the interest of their audience, particularly students. This shows that choosing material and structuring stories to properly hold readers' attention requires careful thought. She stated:

“Especially sa writing, sa critical thinking mostly, because every time na mo write ko og articles gina consider jud nako ang angle sa story, in order nga makuha nako ang interests sa mga, sa audience most specially nga students” (FGD-02)

(Especially in writing, I mostly used critical thinking skills because every time that I write articles I also consider the most accurate angle of the story for me to capture the interest of the audience, especially students.)

Further, Calm (pseudonym) mentioned that he nurtures creativity in writing, attributing the development of this skill to his involvement with the school publication, which also serves as a platform for self-expression. Through her involvement with the publication, she has refined her artistic skills, particularly in the area of writing. He stated:

“I foster a creativity in writing and also tungod aning publication, nag enhance ni sa akoang pagiging creative sa pagsulat and to express myself as a writer” (FGD-06)

(I foster creativity skills in writing, and also because of the school publication, it helped me to develop my creativity, especially in writing, and also it allows me to express myself as a writer.)

Facing Criticism within the Organization

The members of the Collegial shared that they encountered disagreements, constructive criticism, or conflicting perspectives during the process of preparing and producing student publications. It underscores the importance of navigating and addressing criticism effectively within the organizational structure to maintain productive collaboration and improve the quality of the publications.

Smart (pseudonym) mentioned that she was exposed to lots of criticism since she was a new member. She stresses that receiving criticism may be difficult, particularly when it's something you've never done before. "At its finest" implies that the critique could be harsh or significant. The ability to navigate and handle criticism well is essential for new members or writers to develop and adapt. She stated:

“Dealing with criticism, this is the most common challenge na gina encounter sa mga writers, especially if you are a blossoming writer pa, kanang nag start palang jud ka, you will experience criticism at its finest.” (IDI-06)

(Dealing with criticism is the most common challenge encountered by writers, especially if you are still a budding writer who is just starting. You will experience criticism at its finest.)

Furthermore, Criticism (pseudonym) mentioned that dealing with criticism is inevitable, especially for those who work for the school publication. She highlights how their participation in producing news items has increased their prominence and exposed them to criticism. She stated:

“Of course, kani gyung dealing with criticism, like very prone jud kaayo mi sa ingon ani, like diba makita man gyud mi, media man gyud mi, makita man gyud mi ninyo permi like kung mag publish mi especially sa akoo mag cover ko news reports sa page namo.” (IDI-07)

(Of course, when dealing with criticism, we are very prone to this, we can see it, we are in the media, and you can always see us, especially when we publish news reports, I personally cover news reports on our page.)

Moreover, Loud (pseudonym) mentioned that criticism was a typical problem for him and his colleagues when writing pieces for their student journals. Additionally, he highlights that criticism is inevitable when producing articles because of the pressure to meet deadlines and adhere to schedules. The impact of criticisms on their workflow and stress levels is increased by the pressure imposed by these limitations. He stated:

“One problem or challenge nga usually ma experience namo, when we are preparing or producing articles para sa atoang student publication pud is ang criticism gyud kay usually, tungod sa amoang sa short deadlines og sa kaning amoang mga time constraints, kani gyung ang mga criticism jud nato is dili jud nato malikayan samot nag pressure kaayo ta sa, kung mag sulat mig mga articles namo.” (FGD-04)

(One problem or challenge that we usually experience when we are preparing or producing articles for our student publication is criticism. This is mainly because of our short deadlines and time constraints, which make it unavoidable for us to face criticism. Especially when we write our articles, the pressure becomes even greater.)

In addition, Happy (pseudonym) mentioned that he acknowledges criticism as a common challenge within their organization. They distinguish between constructive criticism, which serves as motivation for improvement, and negative criticism, which can lead to feelings of discouragement. He stated:

“Pinaka-common jud namo nga difficulty nga gina change as organization is ang criticism jud. So naay criticism nga kanang open

sya, go siya for improvement, so naa poy uban nga maka down.” (FGD-07)

(One common difficulty that I want to address within our organization is criticism. I do encounter criticism that can be a motivation and a criticism that will make you feel down.)

Having Challenges Due to Inadequacy of Resources

The Collegial members shared that they encounter obstacles such as insufficient funding, equipment, or access to necessary materials. As a result, they may struggle to meet quality standards, adhere to deadlines, or fulfill creative aspirations.

Straight-forward (pseudonym) mentioned that access to various resources and information is not always readily available. This limitation means that it will be difficult to gather materials needed for access to a variety of information sources, and conduct research. She also said that maintaining the quality and completeness of their articles while negotiating these limitations is a constant struggle. She stated:

“The identified constraints that I perceived in preparing and producing student publications include limited resources because I know that not all the time that we have the access to different resources as well as the access to information.” (IDI-05)

Additionally, Smart (pseudonym) mentioned that the scarcity of campus photographers and essential equipment such as cameras, printers, and laptops pose significant challenges. These restrictions made it more difficult to produce publications on time, which could have an impact both on the quality and efficiency of the process. She stated:

“The constraints that I perceived in preparing, and producing student publications. First is the limited resources, in our case, there are only a few campus photographers, and we also have limited materials such as cameras, printers, and laptops that we can use to produce on time.” (IDI-06)

Furthermore, Criticism (pseudonym) mentioned the constraints she faced in preparing and producing student publications, notably limited resources like printing materials. This incident serves as an example of how unanticipated events can worsen resource constraints and cause delays in the production process. She stated:

“The identified constraints that I have perceived in preparing and producing student publication is limited resources, in a way like sa printing materials po sir, like sa printer, diba recently naka experience tag baha, our printer po sir is nadaot, it's because of the unexpected flood.” (IDI-07)

(The constraints I have perceived in preparing and producing student publications include limited resources, such as printing materials, sir. For example, our printer recently got damaged due to unexpected flooding.)

Research Question No. 2: What are the coping strategies of the Collegial members with the challenges in the production of student publications?

To answer this research question, an in-depth interview and focus group discussion were conducted with the informants, respectively, hence, several sub-questions were asked.

The major themes and core ideas for research question number 2 are presented in Table 3. From the answers of the participants, four major themes emerged: managing time strategically, having open communication and effective collaboration, being motivated by passion and purpose, adhering to truth, and fostering trust.

Table 3. Coping Strategies of Collegial Members as They Write Articles for School Publication

<i>Emerging Themes</i>	<i>Supporting Statements</i>
Managing Time Strategically	<p>“At first, it was difficult to adjust to the demands of my organization. However, I became accustomed to it and it somehow became an instinctual part of me even. I learned to juggle my academics and being part of the Collegial as time went on.” — IDI-01</p> <p>“Time management, being organized, and planning ahead of time. Whenever events occur, you will be ready and prepared.” — IDI-02</p> <p>“I handled those challenges in terms of managing my time well which include setting my goals because I cannot provide a valuable and quality output or publication.” — IDI-05</p> <p>“When it comes to adjustments, I have to balance my personal life as well as my responsibility as a student-journalist.” — FGD-01</p> <p>“First is, prioritizing my task, then set deadlines, and create a schedule to manage my time effectively to ensure timely completion of assignments.” — FGD-05</p>
Having Open Communication and Effective Collaboration	<p>“I give credit to our adviser who trusted us wholeheartedly and never failed to guide our steps in the organization. Of course, I had competent co-members who were always there to assist whenever things became hectic. Also, I got a lot to learn from my previous editor-in-chief even at that short period that we got to work together.” — IDI-01</p> <p>“I would like to thank our Collegial adviser, he is an expert and very keen. He is very hands-on in terms of guiding us and very concerned about how the paper is doing, and of course, the members as well. And, to my colleagues that are willing to extend their help.” — IDI-03</p>

Being Motivated by Passion and Purpose	<p>“I cannot be able to produce student publications without the help of our Collegial adviser, my fellow student-journalist, our editors, and our sources and interviewees as well.” — IDI-05</p> <p>“I seek help from our adviser and of course to my fellow student-journalists, since we are open for constructive criticism and that is a big help for us to become better student-journalists.” — FGD-02</p> <p>“My fellow student-journalists helped me to produce a good student publication, also the readers and audience as well.” — FGD-06</p> <p>“For me, is my Collegial adviser and fellow student-journalists. So, if there are suggestions, what to do and to open or venture ideas that will provide us a sense of camaraderie.” — FGD-07</p> <p>“It has been my passion for story-telling that motivated me in producing student publications, and aside from that I always consider my sense of purpose.” — IDI-05</p> <p>“My passion drives me to do better at my work. It is my willingness to enter this organization, so it is my passion that drives me to do better and as well as to give information to the readers and audience.” — FGD-04</p> <p>“I motivate myself in a sense of purpose. I believe in the power of journalism to inform, to educate, and to inspire positive change.” — FGD-05</p> <p>“Writing itself motivates me. Not to brag, but writing is not for everyone. I am very grateful that I possessed this kind of skill that drives my emotion and passion.” — FGD-07</p>
Adhering to Truth and Fostering Trust	<p>“I know that as a journalist, it is very important that you are not biased, that you are not one-sided. Before I produce articles, I need to do fact-checking.” — IDI-05</p> <p>“So, this is an essential part of writing a school paper, because you cannot publish a piece that is not fact-checked and factual in fact.” — IDI-06</p> <p>“Fact-checking is essential for me to provide information that is right as well as relevant or relatable to the readers and audience.” — FGD-04</p>

Managing Time Strategically

The member of the Collegial shared their coping strategies and must juggle academic responsibilities, writing and editing articles, conducting research, and meeting publication deadlines. Collegial members use time management techniques like prioritization, scheduling, and delegation to ensure timely task completion, maintain productivity, minimize stress, and achieve student publications goals.

Intelligent (pseudonym) mentioned that it was difficult for her to adjust to the needs of their organization. However, she adapted to the demands of it and incorporated them into their routine, becoming instinctual. She learned to effectively balance her academic responsibilities with her Collegial role through experience. She stated:

“At first, it was difficult to adjust to the demands of my organization. However, I became accustomed to it and it somehow became an instinctual part of me even. I learned to juggle my academics and my being part of the Collegial as time went on.” (IDI-01)

Furthermore, Optimistic (pseudonym) mentioned that being organized, managing your time, and making proactive plans are crucial to being prepared for future occurrences. He emphasizes that effective resource allocation, information and material organization, and forward planning are all parts of time management, which lowers the possibility of being caught off guard and ensures that tasks and obligations are completed on time. He stated:

“Time management and being organized and planning ahead time. Kay whenever nga for example event comes like naka han-ay na siya.” (IDI-02)

(“Time management, being organized, and planning ahead of time. Whenever events occur, you will be ready and prepared.”)

Moreover, Straight-forward (pseudonym) mentioned that she uses good time management, especially goal-setting, to overcome those difficulties. She guarantees a feeling of direction and purpose in their work by establishing defined goals, which is necessary for generating significant and excellent outputs for their student publication. She stated:

“I handled those challenges in terms of managing my time well which includes effective time management. So, some of the strategies that I imparted on myself include setting my goals, because I cannot produce a valuable and quality output or student publication if I do not set goals for myself.” (IDI-05)

In addition, Editor (pseudonym) mentioned that he needed to find a balance between his personal life and his responsibilities as a student journalist. To effectively manage these obligations, one must devote time and energy to both facets of their lives. He understands how crucial it is to strike a balance between work and personal commitments to guarantee success and general well-being. He stated:

“When it comes to adjustments, I have to balance my personal life as well as my responsibility as a student-journalist.” (FGD-01)

Additionally, Silent (pseudonym) mentioned that she prioritizes her tasks well to efficiently manage her workload. She can concentrate her time on the things that matter by determining which tasks are most important. She establishes a sense of urgency and accountability by setting deadlines, and scheduling enables her to allot the appropriate amount of time to each work. She stated:

“First is, prioritizing my task, then set deadlines, and create a schedule to manage my time effectively and ensure timely completion of

assignments.” (FGD-05)

Having Open Communication and Effective Collaboration

The Collegial members value transparent communication and teamwork while preparing and producing student publications. The members work closely together to accomplish shared objectives, exchange ideas, give feedback, and have frequent, sincere conversations. It depicts a welcoming and inclusive atmosphere where people are at ease voicing their thoughts, settling disputes, and cooperating to achieve a common goal.

Intelligent (pseudonym) mentioned that she expressed her gratitude to her adviser for providing constant support and direction within the company. The mention of capable teammates emphasizes the positive team dynamic in which support for one another eases the strain of stressful circumstances. She also emphasizes the value of cooperation and mentoring by recognizing the insightful education they received from their former editor-in-chief. She stated:

“I give credit to our adviser who trusted us wholeheartedly and never failed to guide our steps in the organization. Of course, I had competent co-members who were always there to assist whenever things became hectic. Also, I got a lot to learn from my previous editor-in-chief even in that short period that we got to work together.” (IDI-01)

Furthermore, Focus (pseudonym) mentioned that he is grateful to his Collegial adviser, highlighting their qualities of sharpness, talent, and attentiveness. The adviser demonstrates a supportive and involved leadership style by being actively involved in the organization's success and taking a hands-on approach. He highlights the adviser's and the group members' vital contributions to the development and success of the group. He stated:

“I would like to thank amoang collegial adviser, very hasa, hawd and very keen. Ano kaayu siya, hands-on kaayu siya and mangutana jud siya kung unsa na among progress karun, until mahuman na ang semester, mag ask siya if kamusta na ang magazine and kamusta na ang mga members. Kanang mga members pud kanang ilahang kuan uhmm willing pud kaayu sila mag tabang.” (IDI-03)

(I would like to thank our collegial adviser, who is very sharp, talented, and very observant. He is very hands-on and always asks about our progress until the end of the semester. He also asks about the magazine and how the members are doing. And, to my colleagues that are willing to extend their help.)

Moreover, Straight-forward (pseudonym) mentioned that she is aware of the teamwork needed to successfully develop student publications. She recognizes the vital role that the Collegial adviser plays in providing direction, the significance of collaboration between editors and student journalists, and the importance of the contributions made by sources and interviewees during the publication process. She stated:

“I cannot be able to produce student publications without the help of our Collegial adviser, my fellow student-journalist, our editors, and our sources and interviewees as well.” (IDI-05)

In addition, White (pseudonym) mentioned how she and the other student journalists worked together, asked their adviser for help, and welcomed constructive criticism. To improve their skills as student journalists, she stresses the importance of asking knowledgeable mentors and peers for advice and criticism. She stated:

“Mag seek jud mi og help sa among adviser and of course sa amoang fellow student journalists, since I mentioned earlier na we are open sa constructive criticism and that is, maka tabang sa amoa nga maging better student journalists.” (FGD-02)

(We seek help from our adviser and of course with my fellow student-journalists, since I mentioned earlier that we are open for constructive criticism and that will help us to become better student-journalists.)

Additionally, Calm (pseudonym) mentioned that creating an outstanding student publication requires teamwork. He thanks readers for their interest in the material, as well as the assistance of colleagues and student journalists in the publication. He highlights the mutually beneficial interaction that exists between the publication's readers and staff, which inspires readers to write interesting content and keeps them motivated. He stated:

“Ang naga tabang sa akoo na mag produce og a good student publication is that first is akoang mga kauban sa publication, mga fellow student journalist and also the readers and audience pud. They help us na kanang pag ganahan sila sa amoang gina published is diba na more motivated mi na mag sulat pa og kanang another story napud para kanang daghan pa og mo basa sa amoang article” (FGD-06)

(What helps me produce a good student publication is first, my colleagues in the publication, fellow student journalists, and also the readers and audience. They help us by showing interest in what we publish, which motivates us to write more stories for more people to read our articles.)

Further, Happy (pseudonym) mentioned that he relies on their collegial adviser, who possesses greater experience within the organization. The adviser's critical critique and feedback improve the quality of the piece, and recognizing other student journalists creates a collaborative atmosphere where peers offer assistance and criticism. He places a strong emphasis on the value of peer contact

and mentoring in promoting organizational development. He stated:

“For me is my Collegial adviser, so naa siyay mas dako nga experience sa amoa within the organization, so naa siyay ma input sa amoang mga output and naa siyay mga criticism pud ba nga maka open og further improvement sa amoang article and sa amoa pud nga as a writer. So aside from our college adviser so naa pud amoang mga fellow student journalists.” (FGD-07)

(For me, it is our collegial adviser, as he has more experience than us within the organization. He provides input on our outputs and offers constructive criticism that opens up opportunities for further improvement in our articles and our writing. Apart from our college adviser, we also have our fellow student journalists.)

Being Motivated by Passion and Purpose

The Collegial members' activities in planning and creating student publications are motivated by a strong feeling of passion and dedication. This theme suggests that contributors are deeply dedicated to their job and the publication's mission, which may include educating readers, elevating student voices, or supporting the school community.

Straight-forward (pseudonym) mentioned that her love of telling stories inspires her and her team to create student publications, and their devotion to the craft ensures that the content is captivating and engaging. She also stresses how crucial it is for student journalists to have a distinct purpose since it gives their work focus and direction. She stated:

“It has been my passion for story-telling that motivated me or myself in producing student publications, and aside from that I always consider my sense of purpose.” (IDI-05)

Furthermore, Loud (pseudonym) mentioned that his enthusiasm for his work serves as his source of inspiration. He emphasizes their desire to keep getting better while expressing a strong sense of dedication and commitment. Furthermore, his emphasis on offering readers and audiences useful information demonstrates their commitment to their roles as information creators and communicators. He stated:

“My passion really drives to be better at my work, so sama sa giingon sakong colleague nga willing mi na nisulod sa kani nga organization, akoa jung passion ang naga drive sa akoa to do better as well as to give informations to the readers or to our audience po” (FGD-04)

(My passion drives me to do better at my work. So, similar to what my colleague said, it is our willingness to enter this organization, so it is my passion that drives me to do better and as well as to give information to the readers and audience.)

Moreover, Silent (pseudonym) mentioned that having a purpose in life is the foundation of her self-motivation. She is motivated by the idea that journalism can enlighten, educate, and motivate constructive change. Their work is motivated by this feeling of purpose, which directs them to maximize the influential potential of journalism. She stated:

“I motivate myself in a sense of purpose. I believe in the power of journalism to inform, to educate, and to inspire positive change.” (FGD-05)

In addition, Happy (pseudonym) mentioned that his love of writing is the source of his underlying inspiration. He considers his ability to write to be a gift or a natural talent, for which he is incredibly grateful. His enthusiasm and feelings are fueled by this admiration, which encourages him to keep improving as a writer and to use his work as a vehicle for artistic expression. He stated:

“Writing itself motivates me, so not to brag but writing is not for everyone, so sa others is naa juy para sa ilaha nga skills jud and for me I think writing and kanang murag grateful ba nga ing-ani ang murag gift or skill nga na tunong sa akoa. Maka drive jud siya sa akong emotion or passion.” (FGD-07)

(Writing itself motivates me, so not to brag, but writing is not for everyone, so for others, they have their skills. For me, I think writing is like a gift or skill that has been bestowed upon me, and I am grateful for it. It drives my emotions or my passion.)

Adhering to Truth and Fostering Trust

The Collegial members prioritize dependability, honesty, and integrity in their work, adhering to journalistic standards, and providing fact-checked articles, and accurate information. They aim to gain audience trust by being believable and true to themselves, fostering a culture of openness and accountability within the publication team.

Straight-forward (pseudonym) mentioned that she understands how important it is to deliver information objectively and without favoritism. She is aware that preserving objectivity is essential to preserving their reporting's credibility and dependability. She makes sure that the material provided to their audience is accurate and dependable by placing fact-checking ahead of article production. She stated:

“I know that as a journalist, it is very important that you are not biased, that you are not one-sided. Before I produce articles, I need to do fact-checking.” (IDI-05)

Furthermore, Smart (pseudonym) mentioned that before being published, stories need to go through a rigorous fact-checking process to guarantee the accuracy and integrity of the facts. She emphasizes how important it is to give accurate, timely information that depicts real events taking place in the community. She highlights that journalists must maintain the reliability and validity of the material published in their school newspaper by abiding by these criteria. She stated:

“So, this is an essential part of writing a school paper, because you cannot publish a piece that is not fact-checked and factual in fact. So, you have to write something that is happening that is true and that is relevant to the community.” (IDI-06)

Moreover, Loud (pseudonym) mentioned their dedication to journalistic integrity by recognizing the significance of providing material that is both approachable and factual. He takes the time to conduct in-depth research, especially for topics that are assigned to him, indicating that he is proactive in upholding the highest standards of reporting. His objective is to maintain the articles' credibility and dependability in the community by emphasizing factual and pertinent content. He stated:

“Fact-checking is essential talaga, para lang gyud nga maka provide mig information nga tama as well as relevant or relatable sa mga readers or audience namo. So ayun, naga hatag kog extra time to research well sa akoang article samot na sa kung asa ko na assign, didto ko mag focus.” (FGD-04)

(Fact-checking is essential so that we can provide accurate information that is also relevant or relatable to our readers or audience. So, I allocate extra time to research thoroughly for my articles, especially for where I am assigned, that is where I focus.)

Research Question No. 3: What are the insights of the Collegial members can share with regards to the production of student publications?

To answer this research question, an in-depth interview and focus group discussion were conducted with the informants, respectively, hence, several sub-questions were asked.

The major themes and core ideas for research question number 3 are presented in Table 4. From the answers of the participants, three major themes emerged: teamwork as a catalyst for success, advocating for the unheard and empowering individuals to achieve excellence, and possessing the versatility and flexibility required.

Table 4. Insights of Collegial Members as They Write Articles for School Publication

<i>Emerging Themes</i>	<i>Supporting Statements</i>
Teamwork as a Catalyst for Success	<p>“The importance of teamwork. I cannot do this one on my own. Through this team, I realized that teamwork is very important, as I have said no man is an island. So, I have a companion in doing things, especially when it comes to publications.” — IDI-07</p> <p>“It is okay to ask for help knowing that I do not have the luxury of time to write articles and also, I ask for help whenever I need a substitute to cover the event if I am not available. So, having reliable co-members as well as advantageous.” — FGD-01</p> <p>“I cannot obtain success if I solely depend on myself, so I should seek help from my colleagues because they might have better ideas than mine.” — FGD-03</p> <p>“Because of the open communication, it paved the way for us to work efficiently. I should not be hesitant to ask for help with my co-members or my adviser to help myself, as well as for me to be able to provide good quality articles.” — FGD-04</p>
Advocating for the Unheard and Empowering Individuals to Achieve Excellence	<p>“I wish to say to writers and journalists like me, is for them to believe that their words on paper are not just mere words. They were given the honor to become the voice of the students, and so, take such voice to serve with purpose and fulfillment.” — IDI-01</p> <p>“I think we are empowered enough to those events that are happening around us, to raise awareness, to share something in the society that would make them realize what is happening right now and it is also a way that empowered people will empower other people who think they are powerless.” — IDI-06</p> <p>“It feels amazing that I am one of the people or students to stand firm or should I say, the voice of all, the voice of the students.” — IDI-07</p> <p>“As someone who strives to inspire others, to value the importance of sincerity and delivering information. To question assumptions and to be the voice of truth who delivers nothing but the truth.” — FGD-01</p> <p>“All in all, my experiences in producing student publications have empowered me to use my voice as a student writer to raise awareness, challenge injustice, and effect positive change within the school community.” — FGD-04</p> <p>“Being a student-writer, I produced a publication which provided data and information that could help my readers an opportunity to practice their writing and also the agree with the idea that as a writer, we become the voice of the voiceless.” — FGD-06</p>
Possessing Versatility and Flexibility is Required	<p>“In the Collegial, you are not only tasked to do the writing but you will be assigned to different responsibilities that will surely require you to utilize other skills.” — IDI-02</p> <p>“You have to adapt to the changes; you have to embrace the beauty of practice and experience.” — IDI-06</p> <p>“I have to adapt innovations. I have to be flexible since media is not constant and it is open to changes.” — IDI-07</p> <p>“I have to consider that we do have our point of view and I need to be open-minded whenever they have</p>

their inputs or feedback.” — FGD-01

“Through practice and experience, it helped me to venture more creative ideas in writing an article and to provide something that will capture the interest of our audience.” — FGD-06

“Before handing in my final manuscript, I mostly make various angles, so I do it by practice and I will see to it that my article will fit exactly for publication.” — FGD-07

Teamwork as a Catalyst for Success

The Collegial members believe that successful planning and production of student publications depend on collaboration. The group members understand the benefits of collaborating to achieve shared objectives. Within the publication team, they value mutual support, shared responsibility, and teamwork. They can overcome obstacles, create powerful content, and create high-caliber publications that connect with their readership thanks to their combined synergy.

Criticism (pseudonym) mentioned the need for cooperation and teamwork, emphasizing that she cannot complete tasks on her own. She has learned the value of collaboration and support from one another through teamwork. She highlights the saying, "No man is an island," emphasizing the innate need for support and companionship to accomplish objectives. She stated:

“The importance of teamwork po sir kasi, we cannot do this one if ever ako lang isa, if ever videographer lang isa, so through ani nga nga team po sir is na realized gyud nako nga it is necessary gyud, very important gyud diay ang teamwork po sir kay kana ganing as what I have said diba no man is an island po, so we have companion in doing things po especially when it comes to publications.” (IDI-07)

(The importance of teamwork, because I cannot do this alone if ever, I am alone, if ever there is only one videographer, so through this team, I realized that it is necessary, teamwork is very important indeed, because as I have said, no man is an island, so we have companions in doing things, especially when it comes to publications.)

Furthermore, Editor (pseudonym) mentioned that he asks for help when she needs it, understanding that their time and availability are limited. He stresses the value of asking for assistance, especially when he needs a stand-in to handle events while he is away. He recognizes the benefit of having a solid support system and appreciates having dependable teammates. He stated:

“It’s okay to ask for help kay knowing nga dili tanan panahon I have enough time to write articles and I also ask for help whenever kailangan nako or need nako og mo substitute na mag cover sa event whenever dili ko available, so having reliable co-members as well is advantageous.” (FGD-01)

(It is okay to ask for help knowing that I do not have enough time to write articles, and also, I ask for help whenever I need a substitute to cover the event if I am not available. So, having reliable co-members as well is advantageous.)

Moreover, Serious (pseudonym) mentioned the drawbacks of depending just on oneself and is an advocate for getting advice from peers, acknowledging that they could have insightful opinions. She also emphasizes how important it is to be open to criticism and ideas and to see them as chances for growth rather than as threats. Her proactive approach to both personal and professional improvement is evident in her acceptance of comments and incorporation of proposed modifications. She stated:

“One of the realizations nga akoang na kuha being part of the organization and sa pag continuously producing sa student publications is dili ka mag succeed if you solely believe sa imong sarili lang. You should seek help sa imohang colleague’s kay they might have better ideas kaysa sa imoha. You should be open for suggestions, kanang ilahang feedback sa imohang article nga gi buhat, and if they suggest something nga need e-edit. You accept it wholeheartedly and take it as a motivation to do better.” (FGD-03)

(One of the realizations I have gained from being part of the organization and continuously producing student publications is that you will not succeed if you solely rely on yourself. You should seek help from your colleagues because they might have better ideas than you. You should be open to suggestions, like their feedback on the articles that you have done, and if they suggest something that needs editing. You accept it wholeheartedly and take it as motivation to do better.)

In addition, Loud (pseudonym) mentioned that he admits to realizing that their job as a team member depends heavily on their ability to communicate. He emphasizes how important it is to ask for help from mentors or coworkers without holding back, realizing that doing so advances one's growth as well as the production of excellent articles. He highlights their dedication to attaining excellence in their profession and helping the magazine succeed by encouraging open communication and teamwork. He stated:

“Because of the open communication, it really pave the way para mabuhat jud amoang work efficiently. So that is one thing that i realize as one of the members in producing student publication. Kana ganing dili jud ka dapat maulaw to ask help sa imohang members or sa inyong advisers para lang gyud matabangan imong kaugalingon as well as para maka deliver pud ka or maka hatag gyud ka og good quality sa imohang gina buhat nga articles.” (FGD-04)

(Because of the open communication, it paves the way for us to efficiently carry out our work. So that is one thing I realize as one of the members in producing student publications. You should not hesitate to ask for help from your members or your advisers just to be able to help yourself as well as to deliver good quality in the articles you produce.)

Advocating for the Unheard and Empowering Individuals to Achieve Excellence The Collegial members recognize the importance of advocacy and representation in their roles of preparing and producing student publications. The members' goal is to provide underrepresented or underprivileged people in their school community with more visibility. They enable people to share their experiences, opinions, and stories by allowing these voices to be heard.

Intelligent (pseudonym) mentioned that their writing is more than just pen and paper; it is a strong voice for the students they are writing for. She exhorts authors and journalists to accept this duty with meaning and fulfillment, realizing the honor bestowed upon them to speak up for the rights of others. She emphasizes the significance of using their position to serve the greater good and bring about positive change in their community by acknowledging the power of their words. She stated:

"I wish to say to writers and journalists like me, is for them to believe that their words on paper are not just mere words. They were given the honor to become the voice of the students, and so, take such voice to serve with purpose and fulfillment." (IDI-01)

Furthermore, Smart (pseudonym) mentioned that by acting, she may draw attention to important problems and encourage people to acknowledge the state of affairs as it is. She also emphasizes how empowered people can encourage and uplift those who might feel helpless, therefore empowering the community as a whole. She emphasizes the transformative power of group action in bringing about good change and encouraging personal empowerment. She stated:

"I think we are empowered enough to those events that are happening around us, to raise awareness, to share something in the society that would make them realize what is happening right now and it is also a way that empowered people will empower other people who think they are powerless." (IDI-06)

Moreover, Criticism (pseudonym) mentioned that she portrays the sense of courage and commitment that comes from speaking up for one's convictions and speaking for the whole student body. She recognizes the value of their voice for others and the necessity of standing out for the concerns and interests of their peers. Her role as an advocate and speaker for the larger community is one of pride and responsibility. She stated:

"Kanang nindot kaayo sa feeling ba na you are one of the people na or a student na kana ganing kibale mo stand firm or should I say kanang ikaw gani ang voice sa tanan, ikaw ang voice sa mga students." (IDI-07)

(That feeling of being one of the people or a student who stands firm, or should I say, being the voice of all, being the voice of the students.)

In addition, Editor (pseudonym) mentioned that he places a strong emphasis on the value of questioning presumptions and acting as an impartial, true voice dedicated to providing correct information. By becoming a beacon of truth, he hopes to inspire others to uphold honesty and integrity in both their words and deeds. He exhibits a commitment to developing communication that is authentic and trustworthy, with an emphasis on encouraging honesty and openness by placing fact-checking ahead of article production. He stated:

"As someone who strives to inspire others, to value the importance of sincerity and delivering information. To question assumptions and to be the voice of truth who delivers nothing but the truth." (FGD-01)

Additionally, Loud (pseudonym) mentioned that he conveys a sense of agency and accountability to confront injustices, spread knowledge, and encourage constructive change among the student body. Their experiences gave him more self-assurance and an understanding of the revolutionary power of journalism as a vehicle for activism and advocacy. He emphasizes his dedication to using his position to make significant and lasting improvements to their educational setting. He stated:

"All in all, my experiences in producing student publications have empowered me to use my voice as a student writer to raise awareness, challenge injustice, and effect positive change within the school community." (FGD-04)

Further, Calm (pseudonym) mentioned that they give readers a chance to interact with writing techniques and even advance their abilities through their publication. He also agrees with the idea that writers frequently act as advocates for underrepresented or silenced voices in society. He has a dedication to using their writing to empower and inform their audience. He stated:

"Being a student-writer, I produced a publication which provided data and information that could help my readers an opportunity to practice their writing and also the agree with idea that as a writer, we become the voice of the voiceless." (FGD-06)

Possessing Versatility and Flexibility is Required

The Collegial members value adaptability in their roles of preparing and producing student publications. They are aware of how dynamic the process is and what the needs of the audience are. They appreciate flexibility in timetables and workflows and can adjust to various jobs, formats, and styles. These attributes facilitate the ability to effectively manage obstacles, explore new opportunities, and generate relevant and captivating articles.

Optimistic (pseudonym) mentioned that writing is only one of the duties that members are expected to perform. In addition to writing, they are required to complete other duties that call for the use of a variety of abilities. These duties probably include editing, taking pictures, covering events, and performing administrative work. They can use and develop a wide range of talents by taking on a variety

of jobs, which enhances their overall development and adaptability within the business. He stated:

“Sa Collegial, dili lang kay assigned ka for writing but pwede ka nga i-ano kanang rumble gud, ma kuan pud imohang other skills.” (IDI-02)

(In the Collegial, you are not only tasked to do writing but you will be assigned to different responsibilities that will surely require you to utilize other skills.)

Furthermore, Smart (pseudonym) mentioned that change is unavoidable and that people must modify their perspectives and strategies accordingly. She can develop resilience and flourish in dynamic circumstances by accepting change. She also emphasizes the importance of ongoing practice and practical experience in honing abilities and successfully overcoming new obstacles. She stated:

“You have to adapt to the changes; you have to embrace the beauty of practice and experience.” (IDI-06)

Moreover, Criticism (pseudonym) mentioned that because the field is dynamic, it is imperative to welcome advances and maintain an open mind. Due to a lack of photographers, she emphasizes their readiness to take on extra duties like acting as photojournalists when needed. Even with their positions growing, they have a willingness to help others, which demonstrates a cooperative and encouraging attitude within their team. She stated:

“Adaptability and flexibility, as I have mentioned earlier, so we have to adapt innovations, we have to be flexible po since ang media man gud is dili lang siya constant ba nga kani, mao na imong buhaton. So we really have to be flexible po, since kami sa karon is gamay ramig photographer, usahay kay ang news reporter musabak mi sa pagka photo journalist, dili lang kay kung unsa amoang role kay mao rana amoang gampanan, but if kaya namo tabangan ang uban po sir so we really do that.” (IDI-07)

(Adaptability and flexibility, as I mentioned earlier, are crucial. We need to embrace innovations and be flexible because the media landscape is not constant; it evolves continuously. Therefore, flexibility is essential. Currently, we have a limited number of photographers, so sometimes, as news reporters, we also take on the role of photojournalists. Our responsibilities extend beyond our designated roles, but if we can help others, we willingly do so.)

In Addition, Editor (pseudonym) mentioned the value of having an open mind and being responsive to the opinions and criticism of others. He exhibits a dedication to inclusivity and teamwork by recognizing that everyone has different opinions. He is aware that taking into account other viewpoints enhances conversations and produces better results. He stated:

“I have to consider that lahi lahi mi og point of views and kailangan ko maging open minded whenever naa silay input or naa silay feedbacks.” (FGD-01)

(I have to consider that we do have our points of view and I need to be open-minded whenever they have their input or feedback.)

Additionally, Calm (pseudonym) mentioned that practicing daily and accumulating practical experience has helped him come up with more creative ideas for their writing. He gained the capacity to create content that effectively piques the interest of their audience by gradually improving his craft. He is now able to consistently hone his writing abilities and produce interesting and captivating pieces because of this iterative process of learning and experimenting. He stated:

“Through practice and experience, it helped me to venture more creative ideas in writing an article and to provide something na kanang very kuan jud kaayo sa panlasa sa mga audience namo.” (FGD-06)

(Through practice and experience, it helped me to venture more creative ideas in writing an article and to provide something that will capture the interest of our audience.)

Further, Happy (pseudonym) mentioned the value of considering several viewpoints when writing, demonstrating his dedication to accuracy and thoroughness. He honed his skills to evaluate and choose the best angle for their piece by practicing. His ultimate objective is to make sure that the completed piece perfectly complies with the publication's guidelines and specifications. He stated:

“Before mag hatag jud ko sa akoang final nako nga manuscript, so gahimo kog daghag mga angles, so I do it by practice gani sa akoang article nga I see fit nga pwedi na sya for publication.” (FGD-07)

(Before handing in my final manuscript, I mostly make various angles, so I do it by practice and I will see to it that my article will fit exactly for publication.)

Conclusions

The result of this study presented how the Collegial members did believe in the appropriate actions of being a responsible writer. For them, practice is the key to continuous improvement. They stated that as a writer, having the skills and knowledge is the primary factor that would make the article more comprehensive.

Moreover, the result also identified the coping strategies of the participants such as; managing time strategically, having open communication and effective collaboration, being motivated by passion and purpose, adhering to truth, and fostering trust. They were

motivated to do well because of how they accepted the fact that as a writer, it is a must to cope effectively to learn more. They acknowledge that accepting challenges is not a defeat but a winning action for those who want to learn.

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